

IPBES AR BBA Chapter 2 – Snowballing literature search for literature on business dependency on biodiversity (A)

Initial set of papers for the snowball literature search

	Reference
1	Breeze, T. D., Gallai, N., Garibaldi, L. A., & Li, X. S. (2016). Economic Measures of Pollination Services: Shortcomings and Future Directions. <i>Trends in Ecology & Evolution</i> , 31(12), 927–939. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2016.09.002
2	Breeze T.D., Garratt M.P.D., Senapathi D., Willcox B.K. and Potts S.G 2022 Economic Benefits of Pollination to Global Food Systems – Evidence and Knowledge Gaps: Final Report https://www.ukri.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/NERC-281022-EconomicBenefitsPollinationGlobalFoodSystems-FullReport.pdf
3	Brunetti, I., Tidball, M., & Couvet, D. (2019). Relationship between biodiversity and agricultural production. <i>Natural Resource Modelling</i> , 32(2), e12204. https://doi.org/10.1111/nrm.12204
4	Carvalho, S. H. C. D., Cojoianu, T., & Ascui, F. (2023). From impacts to dependencies: A first global assessment of corporate biodiversity risk exposure and responses. <i>Business Strategy and the Environment</i> , 32(5), 2600–2614. https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3142
5	Dasgupta, P. (2021), The Economics of Biodiversity: The Dasgupta Review. Abridged Version. (London: HM Treasury).
6	Grigorov, B. & Assenov, A. 2019. Bulgarian ecosystems/landscapes – A setting for Hollywood movies. International Seminar for of Ecology -2019. Proceedings18-19 April 2019, Sofia, Bulgaria.
7	Gutierrez-Arellano, C., & Mulligan, M. (2018). A review of regulation ecosystem services and disservices from faunal populations and potential impacts of agriculturalisation on their provision, globally. <i>Nature Conservation</i> , 30, 1–39. https://doi.org/10.3897/natureconservation.30.26989
8	Hanley, N., & Perrings, C. (2019). <i>The Economic Value of Biodiversity</i> . https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-resource-100518-093946
9	Harrison, P. A., Berry, P. M., Simpson, G., Haslett, J. R., Blicharska, M., Bucur, M., Dunford, R., Egoh, B., Garcia-Llorente, M., Geamănă, N., Geertsema, W., Lommelen, E., Meiresonne, L., & Turkelboom, F. (2014). Linkages between biodiversity attributes and ecosystem services: A systematic review. <i>Ecosystem Services</i> , 9, 191–203. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2014.05.006
10	Houdet, J., Trommetter, M., & Weber, J. (2012). Understanding changes in business strategies regarding biodiversity and ecosystem services. <i>Ecological Economics</i> , 73, 37–46. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2011.10.013
11	Kennedy, C. M., Miteva, D. A., Baumgarten, L., Hawthorne, P. L., Sochi, K., Polasky, S., Oakleaf, J. R., Uhlhorn, E. M., & Kiesecker, J. (2016). Bigger is better: Improved nature conservation and economic returns from landscape-level mitigation. <i>Science Advances</i> , 2(7), e1501021. https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1501021
12	Liu, W., Antonelli, M., Kummu, M., Zhao, X., Wu, P., Liu, J., Zhuo, L., & Yang, H. (2019). Savings and losses of global water resources in food-related virtual water trade. <i>WIREs Water</i> , 6(1), e1320. https://doi.org/10.1002/wat2.1320

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13	Mitova, R., Borisova, B., & Koulov, B. (2021). Digital Marketing of Bulgarian Natural Heritage for Tourism and Recreation. <i>Sustainability</i> , 13(23), 13071. https://doi.org/10.3390/su132313071
14	Moreaux, C., Meireles, D. A. L., Sonne, J., Badano, E. I., Classen, A., González-Chaves, A., Hipólito, J., Klein, A.-M., Maruyama, P. K., Metzger, J. P., Philpott, S. M., Rahbek, C., Saturni, F. T., Sritongchuay, T., Tschardtke, T., Uno, S., Vergara, C. H., Viana, B. F., Strange, N., & Dalsgaard, B. (2022). The value of biotic pollination and dense forest for fruit set of Arabica coffee: A global assessment. <i>Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 323, 107680. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2021.107680
15	Nedkov, S., Borisova, B., Nikolova, M., Zhiyanski, M., Dimitrov, S., Mitova, R., Koulov, B., Hristova, D., Prodanova, H., Semerdzhieva, L., Dodev, Y., Ihtimanski, I., & Stoyanova, V. (2021). A methodological framework for mapping and assessment of ecosystem services provided by the natural heritage in Bulgaria. <i>Journal of the Bulgarian Geographical Society</i> , 45, 7–18. https://doi.org/10.3897/jbgs.e78680
16	Nedkov, S., Mitova, R., Nikolova, M., Borisova, B., Hristova, D., Semerdzhieva, L., Zhiyanski, M., & Prodanova, H. (2021). Prioritization of ecosystem services related to the natural heritage of Bulgaria. <i>Journal of the Bulgarian Geographical Society</i> , 45, 19–30. https://doi.org/10.3897/jbgs.e73687
17	Schröter, M., Koellner, T., Alkemade, R., Arnhold, S., Bagstad, K. J., Erb, K.-H., Frank, K., Kastner, T., Kissinger, M., Liu, J., López-Hoffman, L., Maes, J., Marques, A., Martín-López, B., Meyer, C., Schulp, C. J. E., Thober, J., Wolff, S., & Bonn, A. (2018). Interregional flows of ecosystem services: Concepts, typology and four cases. <i>Ecosystem Services</i> , 31, 231–241. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2018.02.003
18	Skouloudis, A., Malesios, C., & Dimitrakopoulos, P. G. (2019). Corporate biodiversity accounting and reporting in mega-diverse countries: An examination of indicators disclosed in sustainability reports. <i>Ecological Indicators</i> , 98, 888–901. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2018.11.060
19	TNC, 2015. Upper Tana-Nairobi Water Fund Business Case. Version 2. The Nature Conservancy: Nairobi, Kenya.
20	Watson, S., & Newton, A. (2018). Dependency of Businesses on Flows of Ecosystem Services: A Case Study from the County of Dorset, UK. <i>Sustainability</i> , 10(5), 1368. https://doi.org/10.3390/su10051368